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Status of Underutilized Crops in Ethiopia: Opportunities, Challenges and Policy Recommendations for Development of Underutilized Crops

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Abstract

Underutilized crops are an important part of agro-biodiversity, and they have the potential to help poor rural communities adapt to climate change, enhance food security, and gain food sovereignty. Despite increased interest in research, they remain on the peripheries of the agricultural mainstream. Its main goal is to give policy suggestions for supporting the production, conservation, and expanded use of underutilized crops for improved food and livelihood security, particularly for Ethiopia's rural poor. A survey study and literature analysis were used to assess the state of Ethiopia's underutilized crops in order to identify existing gaps, opportunities, challenges, and potential future policy suggestions and guidelines. According to the study, Ethiopia's food and agricultural legislation and policy frameworks allow certain opportunities for the development and use of underutilized crops, but the majority of them do not support or favor these crop products. From agricultural research, production, and extension to agricultural marketing and the country's approach to food security, Ethiopia's policy planning is tilted towards promoting the large crops at the expense of the rural poor people's crops—the underutilized crops. This is unfortunate because many Ethiopian households, especially those in rural areas where the majority of the population resides, rely on these crops not just for food and nutrition but also for income and overall stability. Reforming Ethiopia's food and agricultural policy is also crucial to ensuring that underutilized crops are adequately supported in order to improve Ethiopians' food and livelihood security, particularly in rural areas. It's crucial to identify underutilized crops with the greatest potential for success and the ability to be incorporated into a variety of production or cropping systems, as well as to prioritize them for future research, development, and innovation

Keywords: climate change; challenges; food and nutrition security; opportunities; sustainability

Introduction

The modern agriculture system and recent technologies are promoting the production and productivity of high-input and high-yielding crop species, with the intensification of a limited number of crop species, especially the only cereal crops. This has led to a decline in crop diversity and a monotonous nutrition system in agricultural systems across the world, which has been associated with a diminishing of nutrition diversity and a decline in the regulatory services of the environment. Different agricultural and development programs were not focused on analyzing local opportunities for the community's livelihood based on local crop species and other local agricultural resources; rather, orienting the production and farming systems toward high-input and only high

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yielding crops is the only option for uplifting the livelihoods of the farmers (John *et al.*, 2006). Especially, the cultivation and production of underutilized or neglected crops has declined and continues to decline all over the world; even though such crops provide greater potential to improve the food and nutritional security of communities. This is particularly important to ensure food and nutritional security for the current increasing population in a world of limited resources (Hughes, 2008).

For developing countries, new approaches, strategies, and policies are important to ensure food and nutrition security. These should be sustainable, resilient, and practical solutions to solve the food security problem in drought-prone countries like Ethiopia. Given this context, crop diversity, especially neglected or underutilized crops, is essential to addressing food and nutrition security and mitigating the impacts of climate change (Mabhaudhi *et al.*, 2019). They are nutrient-rich crops that demonstrate the potential for adaptation and productions on several continents, reinforcing the importance of crop diversity in the face of food shortages and climate change, which must be a priority in future, research (Manners, 2018).

It is instructive to note that the majority of the food insecure, hungry, poor and vulnerable Ethiopians live in rural areas and depend on agriculture for food, income, and livelihood security. Part of the problem is that the government, the private sector, and development partners often focus their efforts in the fight against food insecurity and hunger on a few major crops that are considered important for food security (Regassa and Management, 2011). They often ignore or give very little attention to underutilized crops such as mushrooms, yams, indigenous fruits, and vegetables. Peter (2008), yet millions of Ethiopians in rural marginal areas rely on these crops for their sustenance and livelihood security. If given the necessary policy attention, these crops have great potential not only to improve the food and nutrition security of the people in rural areas but also to provide and improve income opportunities for the most vulnerable in these areas, particularly the women and the youth. It is from the above context that this paper sets out to examine Ethiopia's agriculture and food security-related policies and policy frameworks to provide recommendations that can be adopted to scale up the production and use of underutilized crops in Ethiopia (Regassa^b and Management, 2011). The paper has three specific objectives. First, it aims to identify the overall gaps or challenges concerning the production and utilization of underutilized crops in Ethiopia. Second, it aims to identify the existing policy opportunities for promoting underutilized crops in Ethiopia's development. Finally, the paper provides policy recommendations or guidelines that can be taken to support the production and wider use of underutilized crops in improving food and income security in Ethiopia. Generally, the main objectives are to: assess the challenges and opportunities for exploitation of the underutilized crops in Ethiopia; and develop a guideline (proposing recommendations) for the promotion and development of underutilized crops in Ethiopia.

2. Underutilized Crops' Contribution to National Development

Underutilized crops are those that have a lot of promise for food production and development, but their potential isn't properly acknowledged or exploited. Underutilized crops are also known as "minor crops," "neglected species," "orphan crops," "underdeveloped species," and "underexploited species," among other terms (Wenhold *et al.*, 2007). They are referred to as "minor" crops or species since their commercial value of production and trade is low in comparison to the main crops/species (Srivastava *et al.*, 2017). The term "neglected" refers to the fact that underutilized crops receive very little research and development attention in comparison to major crops (Tadele, 2019). As a result, the vast majority of them are poorly characterized, with little scientific information available about them. As a result, these crops are still "underutilized" in terms of national development. One thing to keep in mind with underutilized crops is that they differ from one location to the next (Azam-Ali *et al.*, 2001). In Kenya and Rwanda, what may be an underutilized crop in Ethiopia or elsewhere might become a big crop. Even within a single country, underutilized crops might vary from region to region, however, several crops can be found in both.

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So, the necessity for Ethiopia to promote the production and use of underutilized crops can be justified for five primary reasons. To begin with, the bulk of these crops and species are frequently farmed by impoverished farmers and communities in marginal and fragile habitats such as dry lands and wetlands, which are not conducive to the growth and production of more commonly used crops. The majority of underutilized crops are resistant to harsh weather and environmental extremes. Underutilized crops are thus not "small crops" to many farmers living in marginal locations. They are the foundation of their agricultural systems and are essential to their livelihoods and food security. Given the current threat of climate change and its implications for food and agricultural output, boosting underutilized crops is a key policy option for guaranteeing food and livelihood security for the poor rural masses living in marginal areas.

Second, there is mounting evidence that many underutilized crops are extremely nutritious, providing several nutrients and other health benefits that far outnumber those provided by mainstream crops (Ebert, 2014). Promoting the production and greater use of these crops should therefore be a vital part of the government's efforts to combat malnutrition, as well as malnutrition-related diseases and fatalities, which, as mentioned earlier, are highly common in Ethiopia. Third, unlike main crops, underutilized crops require fewer pesticide and fertilizer inputs. Many underutilized crops, in fact, are pest and disease resistant. This means that rural poor farmers can grow neglected crops at a low cost and in a long-term manner. Given the terrible cycle of poverty that the majority of Ethiopia's farmers are trapped in, this is crucial.

Fourth, underutilized crops provide a significant source of income and empowerment, particularly for women, who are the primary cultivators. There is evidence that a large percentage of Ethiopia's underutilized crops make it to market, particularly in the geographical areas where they are farmed (Gebreselassie, 2006). Given that agriculture is the primary source of income for individuals living in rural regions and that women farm the majority of underutilized crops, these crops are a vital source of income and empowerment for vulnerable women. Promoting underutilized crops can thus be a useful policy tool in the fight against poverty and women's empowerment.

Over and above the aforementioned advantages, underutilized crops are vital not just for the preservation of agricultural biodiversity, but also for the long-term sustainability of food and agricultural production. The general decline and erosion of Ethiopia's underutilized crops/species (due to neglect) could erode the genetic foundation and impede the utilization of specific valuable features in agricultural adaptation and improvement. This would be miserable, especially given Ethiopia's rapid population expansion, which requires additional food and income-generating activities for the country's overall survival, not to mention the threat of climate change, which could make today's major crops unsustainable. Underutilized crops must therefore be promoted as a primary means of preserving and conserving agricultural biodiversity for current and future generations.

2.1 Factors Influencing the Promotion and Development of Underutilized Crops

Technological and scientific supports for the big crops (e.g., maize, rice, wheat, and potato), large-scale adoption of monocultures, as well as economic incentives for select crops, have to a great extent stalled the adoption of crop diversification. Global attention is increasingly shifting towards sustainable agricultural systems (Samberg *et al.*, 2016). However, as the prevalence of smallholders varies between Africa, Asia, and Latin America, so do the farming practices and dimensions of rural poverty. This should be a key consideration in developing policies and technologies that improve productivity and uplift the rural poor more effectively (Kassie *et al.*, 2018).

2.1.1 Resources and Knowledge Systems

Large-scale cultivation of the big crops generated significant emphasis on the research of these main crops, such as on disease infection and resistance patterns (Mustafa *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, it results in neglecting the study of underutilized crops and their role within their communities (Cheng *et al.*, 2019). The domestication and introduction of underutilized crops will be largely influenced by our current knowledge of these crops. Crop improvement programs are dependent on the availability of knowledge on the variability within germplasm collections (Ahmad *et al.*, 2016).

This disparity in our available knowledge can even be seen in the research carried out on the agronomic practices of crop production as well as its response to climate change. Agronomic practices of underutilized crops remain understudied, while rapid developments in the fields of precision agriculture of major crops have been witnessed that allow for optimizing irrigation and chemical input (Mayes *et al.*, 2019). Dedicated models have been established for forecasting cropping outcomes under various climate change scenarios, such as CERES-wheat and CERES-rice (Lin, 2011; Lin *et al.*, 2017). These models are very powerful, with the ability to estimate various climate change scenarios as well as different agricultural farming systems, yet very little has been done on studying the response of underutilized crops (Karunaratne *et al.*, 2014).

Nonetheless, the availability of general information might not always be a limiting factor in the adoption of crop diversification systems. In a study by Mango *et al.* (2018), greater access to general information and an increase in years of farming experience were found to be inversely related to the adoption of diversification systems, with a 29.7% and 5.5% decrease, respectively, in the probability of adopting diversification reported. Alternatively, a positive relationship was reported between land size holding and the adoption of crop diversification (Mango *et al.*, 2018).

2.1.2 Technology

The advancement of technologies has been specifically targeted towards the big crops, with little relevance to the variety of other crops available. Molecular technologies generated significant data on the main crops, such as gene expression under abiotic stresses (Bonthala *et al.*, 2016). Unfortunately, these technologies such as microarrays have yet to be developed for the research of underutilized crops. However, through the adoption of other technologies such as Next Generation Sequencing, the available knowledge on the main crops can be integrated to generate data on underutilized crops (Mayes *et al.*, 2019).

Technologies can play a pivotal role in reducing rural poverty by improving resilience and closing the potential yield gap. This requires broader investment in agricultural research as well as policy support to allow for more effective research uptake and technology adoption by the communities (Kassie *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, for agricultural research to be beneficial to the rural poor, it must be demand-driven and consider the structural differences between farming communities across different continents.

2.1.3 Farming Systems

Modern agricultural systems are increasingly dependent on monoculture farming systems that constantly require external input and infrastructure (Altieri and Sustainability, 1999). These systems generally view the integration of biodiversity as a competition for resources, hindering productivity (Kremen *et al.*, 2012). Large-scale adoption of such farming systems has contributed to improved biomass production but at an expensive environmental cost. Such systems reduce biodiversity while degrading natural resources, resulting in soil erosion and increased run-off from chemical fertilizers and pesticides.

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The mechanization of farming practices reduces labor costs and time but is only effective when single crops of uniform variety are cultivated, as activities such as planting, irrigation, and harvesting can be carried out uniformly (Lin, 2011). This development has brought about a scale-up in crop production and stability in food prices in the short term, becoming the norm for modern agricultural practices. As long as national and global interests remain solely focused on increasing immediate output, rather than on the functionality, and well-being of the agro-ecosystem, such practices will continue to take precedence over sustainable agricultural farming systems. Food sovereignty is negatively impacted by national policies that focus on yield, discouraging the cultivation of local crops that are more adapted to the regional climate and less susceptible to global economic impacts (Kijima *et al.*, 2011). Such policies that emphasize intensification and the use of external farming inputs disadvantage smallholder farmers and show little regard for the local needs of the community (Sisifa *et al.*, 2016).

Smallholder farms account for 30% of the global agricultural sphere, playing a key role in sustaining the food needs of vulnerable populations (Samberg *et al.*, 2016). These systems tend to adopt sustainable cropping systems that support social, economic, and environmental needs (Samberg *et al.*, 2016). It is a carefully planned approach that considers the functional biodiversity and biotic interactions of the system. Thus, they are capable of coexisting with threatened and marginal landscapes, maximizing the benefits of ecosystem services for a productive and sustainable agricultural system (Kremen *et al.*, 2012).

2.1.4 Investment and Financial Support

National economic incentives have shown a longstanding preference towards monoculture farming systems, with government subsidies made available to select main crops. As an example, the United States offers subsidies for the cultivation of rice, wheat, maize, soybeans, and cotton (Lin, 2011). According to Boody *et al.* (2009), 89% of the agricultural subsidies in 1995–2002 were allocated to the cultivation of these crops, with maize and soybean receiving 56% of the subsidies. Moreover, maximizing production of single crops is further encouraged by these subsidies that are allocated based on the acreage of crops farmed.

The US is not alone in the adoption of such policies. African governments have also placed significant effort into enhancing agricultural productivity by developing subsidy programs for specific crops, particularly maize (Saenz and Thompson, 2017). The Zambian government recently acknowledged the impact of this policy on increasing production risk due to increased specialization in input-dependent crops (Sisifa *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, Sri Lanka's national emphasis on rice has encouraged its farmers to focus on the cultivation of this water-intensive crop in a region that has suffered numerous drought spells with the advent of climate change (Mustafa *et al.*, 2019). With no subsidies available for other less-water-demanding crops, households will continue to struggle with the cultivation of rice.

The liberalization of agricultural policies and markets means that farmers are now exposed to global fluctuations in produce prices, regardless of domestic conditions (Pellegrini and Tasciotti, 2014; Dawson *et al.*, 2016). Thus, small farmers producing global crops struggle to compete with large producers in the global market, with cheap imported grains flooding the local market. Crop diversification addresses this challenge and minimizes the external influences of the big players, encouraging small farmers to produce diverse crops for their local market. However, this external influence is encroaching on the lands of smallholders due to the increasing acquisition of farmland by foreign investors.

3. Conceptual Framework

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Consolidating previous activities, establishing new objectives that accommodate specific NUS with potential, and ensuring that future research targets all parts of the stakeholders and the value chain are all significant goals of the policy and plan. Prioritization and research are universally accepted as essential components of any effective and cohesive strategic plan for the development of this sector. Priority setting on the research, challenges, and opportunities can be considered as a process of determining actions that provide the most value and have the best chances of success for NUS development in the framework of this strategy. Prioritization and research efforts harmonize activities that will allow NUS to be mainstreamed into current farming and cropping systems. Prioritization of opportunities and challenges should (i) manage all resources appropriately (Kassie *et al.*) allow for research and farming system development, (iii) enhance stakeholder involvement Mabhaudhi *et al.* (2017) allow the use of beneficial technologies and (iii) Enhance the market development and value chain. These characteristics align with Figure 1's six-step priority-setting approach and the establishment of guidelines or policy recommendations for the NUS development plan.

Figure 1: Concepts of strategies recommendation for the development and promotion of underutilized crops in Ethiopia (Source: Developed by student researcher from a literature review and own understanding, 2021)

4. Research Approaches

4.1. Description of the Study Area

GutoGida is one of the woredas in the Oromia Region of Ethiopia. It is part of the East Wollega Zone. It is bounded by Wayu Tuka in the east, Sasiga and Diga in the west, Gida Ayana and Gudaya Bila in the north, and Leka Dulacha to the south. Mixed agriculture is the major livelihood strategy in the study area. In this system crop and livestock production prevails. The cereals crop production is the common farming system of Rain-fed

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maize, sorghum, millet, and teff are the main sources of food in the farming system while sesame and niger seed are mostly grown for market.

There are also mixed cropping practices in some of the study areas that include: Maize + haricot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*), Maize +pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*), Maize+ Cabbage (*Birassicaoleracea*), Maize) + Sweet potato + Anchote + Oromo Dinich + Taro in mid highland of the study area. However, there is a limited production of underutilized and neglected crops such as DinnichaOromoo (*Coleus edulis*), Anchote, sweet potato, Taro, Mungbeans, some Legume crops, Amaranths, some leaf vegetables, some pulses, Pumpkins, Inset, Millet and Forest products crops in the household of the study area (Negasa, 2013).

In GutoGida district, there is a concentration of neglected and underutilized crops and there is a crop production type variation among the farmers. Wollega Zones are identified as historically important farming regions with a considerable amount of underutilized root crops (Desta, 2010). GutoGida district will be purposely selected for this study since it belongs to the east Wollega zone where many farming regions of underutilized crops could be observed.

4.2. Research Design

For the study's outcome investigations, a combination of qualitative and quantitative research approaches was applied. The paper is largely based on a desk review and survey interview of the relevant policy frameworks and other limiting factors connected to it. It was focused on identifying the policy gaps or challenges regarding promoting underutilized crops in Ethiopia, identifying the major existing policy opportunities for promoting underutilized crops in Ethiopia, and suggesting policy recommendations for promoting underutilized crops. Overall, this paper is a review and survey study that focuses on identifying opportunities and challenges for the development and promotion of underutilized crops in Ethiopia and other African countries, and possible recommendations for promoting underutilized crops are suggested. The current paper provides more specific analyses of Ethiopia and other East African countries. A mixed-methods review approach, which included combining quantitative and qualitative research or outcomes, was used to compile the review. Emphasis was placed on the use of literature from Ethiopia and other African countries, with limited comparisons to international literature; this allowed for an assessment of local knowledge relative to international knowledge on neglected and underutilized crop species (NUS). Articles were identified through searches on Google Scholar databases for the period from 2000 to August 2021. In addition, the professional interview of stakeholders was undertaken in the GutoGida district of the East Wollega zone of Ethiopia.

4.3. Sampling and Data Collection Technique

The identification of study literature relevant to Ethiopian underutilized or indigenous agricultural species was prioritized. The keywords or words often used to refer to underutilized crops in Ethiopia and other East African nations were initially found using an online literature search. (i) underutilized crops, Kassie *et al.* (2018) indigenous crops, (iii) traditional crops, and (v) neglected crops were found as the four most frequently and generally used phrases. This terminology search was based on the findings of the initial research (Joshi *et al.*, 2020). Google and Google Scholar, Science Direct, and Springer Link search engines were used to conduct online searches. Articles about Ethiopia were of particular interest, and other African nation literature was used to narrow down the results.

Primary data was obtained from the study area population and agricultural officials for the opportunities and challenges for the development and promotion of underutilized crops were collected from the selected households and agricultural officers' interviews were conducted focusing on the determinant factories for the

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development of underutilized crops. A semi-structured questionnaire was utilized to collect quantitative data from household heads in three Kebeles: Abdeta, Nagassa, and Qitesa, to generate primary data. A total of 18 key informant households were chosen for the survey (12 male-headed households and 6 female-headed households). A survey of underutilized crop producers and non-producers was undertaken once. To obtain primary data, the study used a home questionnaire survey, focus groups, and key informant interviews.

4.4. Data Analysis Techniques

An analysis of variance was performed on the data. SPSS was used for the statistical analysis. The SPSS Least Significant Difference (LSD) with a significance level of 5% was used to separate the means. The coefficients of variation were calculated using the means, standard errors, and least significant differences (LSD) (Singh *et al.*, 1997). To determine the relationship between all parameters, a linear correlation was used. The SPSS computer software package was used to evaluate the quantitative data gathered mostly from household surveys.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Overview of Farming and Cropping Systems in Ethiopia and Other African Countries

Ethiopian farming and cropping practices are largely influenced by the agro-ecological zone in which they are located. According to agroecological zones developed by MOA and EIAR, the country may be categorized into three agroecological zones based on altitude and temperature averages: low land, mid-high land, and high land production zones. As a result, the discussion on farming and cropping systems will concentrate on their suitability for smallholder farmers in mid-highland and highland climates.

Smallholder populations consume a variety of NUS, including cereals, legumes, root and tuber vegetables, and leafy greens. The short growing season, high nutrient content, low agronomic requirements, drought resistance, unique and acquired taste, and abundance in the wild have all contributed to the appeal of leafy vegetables, also known as African Leafy Vegetables (ALVs) (Mustafa *et al.*, 2019). In East African countries, there are more than 42 NUS documented in use (Modi and Mabhaudhi, 2014). The diversity of NUS was found to be higher in the mid-high land zone, where they are harvested, grown, and traded in informal markets. The potential of NUS under water scarcity in lowland and mid-highland areas has previously been established (Chivenge *et al.*, 2015).

Because most NUS are resistant to a variety of environmental stress conditions, they should be promoted in agricultural-producing areas with limited resources. Their huge genetic pool represents a significant subset of agro-biodiversity, hence promoting landscape diversity in remote locations (Galluzzi *et al.*, 2010). NUS promotion in smallholder communities should not aim to replace current major crops; rather, it should focus on diversifying current cropping systems to reduce the current global cropping system, which is characterized by low agro-biodiversity, with only five crops accounting for more than 60% of daily calorific intake (maize, wheat, rice, potato, and sorghum). Through increased food options, availability, and access, there is a clear link between high agro-biodiversity and food and nutrition security (Kumar *et al.*, 2015). As a result, enhanced agro-biodiversity, as a result of NUS promotion, can improve food options, resulting in improved food sovereignty and livelihoods for smallholder communities. The role of NUS in Ethiopia and other African households' food consumption patterns is highly diverse and is influenced by characteristics such as economic status, degree of urbanization, distance to fresh produce markets, and time of year (Ng'endo *et al.*, 2016). It could be argued that consumption of NUS has always been a livelihood strategy by smallholder farmers located in marginal areas.

5.2. Production Status of NUS in Ethiopia

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By 2030, Ethiopia's population is predicted to grow to 145.5 million Benson *et al.* (2005), and the proportion of the population suffering from malnutrition will rise. To address this issue, more than a 45% increase in food production is needed (Ketema, 1993). Expanding the area under cultivation, breeding for new high-producing varieties, and improving resource efficiency are all suggested strategies for enhancing agricultural production. Ethiopia possesses unused land, mostly in rural areas, but agriculture is hampered by a lack of water. As a result, the focus on resource efficiency has shifted to enhancing water efficiency. Emphasis on production diversification using underutilized crops is a possible option that could be pursued to boost agricultural yield and production sustainability. They can (i) increase the amount of area under cultivation; Kassie *et al.* (2018) diversify crop varieties for future sustainable production; and (iii) improve resource utilization efficiency (land and water). The underutilization of NUS presents an opportunity for the creation of new value chains to promote rural agriculture development and food security. The research value chain, which includes breeding/crop enhancement, production, agro-processing, and marketing, can help achieve this.

5.3. Ethiopia's Underutilized Crop Promotion Status and Policy Gaps

Although Ethiopia's agricultural and food security policies unquestionably encourage the production, protection, and use of underutilized crops in national development, the majority of them do not. Ethiopia's policy planning is often not supportive of the role of underutilized crops in national development, from agricultural research, production, and extension to agricultural marketing and the country's approach to food security. In terms of the production, conservation, and use of underutilized crops, this section emphasizes the inadequacies in Ethiopia's agricultural and food security policy.

Starting with agricultural production and marketing, Ethiopia has started to follow a zonal agricultural production, agro-processing, and marketing policy in recent years, in which the country has been divided into zones of production excellence (Gebreselassie, 2006). Climate variances, socioeconomic traits, and the need for sufficient land under production for selected high-value companies were all used to map out the zones. The enterprises for each zone were chosen based on factors such as product availability and accessibility to regional and international markets; product competitiveness and Ethiopia's comparative advantage; product profitability; zone potential to produce targeted products on a long-term basis; and production, processing, and marketing constraints.

Ethiopia's export plan does not include the promotion of underutilized crops for national growth. Although it calls for broadening Ethiopia's exports to include a wide range of items (Moreda, 2017), it focuses on the traditional key crops that are already in demand on the international market for agricultural exports.

5.4. Challenges and Opportunities for Full Utilization of Underutilized Crops in Ethiopia

Following the exercise in developing and promoting underutilized crops, various open-ended questioners, group discussions, key informant interviews, and personal observations from the study area, district, and zone agricultural offices were used to assess the challenges, barriers, and opportunities for all activities and development opportunities. On the general obstacles and prospects of implementing underutilized crops, 15 informant persons from households, professionals, and officers were interviewed, as well as six group discussions and eight key informant interviews. The primary goal was to identify the major issues for NUS in terms of research, development, and innovation, which would serve as a road map for future national promotion and funding. Second, to find ways to promote and grow the contribution of these underutilized crops in such a way that the national development plan and food security challenges are addressed.

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The challenges identified were lack of awareness, institutional and organizational involvement, limited sources of funding, limited sources of production materials, lack of emphasis from concerned bodies, farmers' adaptation to crop diversification, and limited firm policies and strategies on the development and promotion of crop diversification (Fig. 4.4). On the other hand, the characteristics of its opportunities were identified: it is easily produced in a small area of land, easily cultivated in local materials, has a short maturity stage, has a high productive or yield potential, is drought and stress tolerant, contains dense and good nutrition value, has high demand and high market value, has high social and cultural value, and creates job opportunities (Fig 2).

5.4.1. Challenges

According to the results of this survey, the most problematic problems for professionals, offices, and even farmers themselves are a lack of firm development and promotion policies and strategies for crop diversification with underutilized crops (Fig. 2). The most challenging problem in the research area as well as the country was the lack of government attention to the farming system, particularly crop diversification. According to the findings of this study, government policies, plans, and follow-up concentrated solely on cereal crop production and a specialized agricultural system rather than crop diversification. Furthermore, 71 percent of respondents said that a lack of production resources, such as improved and readily available seed and other inputs was one of the most difficult problems in this region (Fig. 2). The greatest challenge in this area, according to 50% of respondents, is a lack of awareness and excellent information about the overall implementation of crop diversity.

Furthermore, as this result demonstrates, the lack of participation of various institutions and organizations, as well as a lack of financing sources for the development of this field, is another problematic issue in the research area as well as for the country. The promotion of NUS policy and strategy can only be successful if it is backed up by, linked to, and connected with international, regional, and national policies (RISDP, 2015). The National Integrated Growth and Development Planning (IGDP) (2010), the National Department of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (DAFF) Strategic Plan for 2016–2020, the National Food Security Production Programme, and the National Policy on Food and Nutrition Security are all aligned with the high-yielding crops promotion strategy (2014). All of these programs emphasize the importance of increasing smallholder participation in mainstream agriculture and the adoption of sustainable farming techniques to promote food and nutrition security in households.

As a result, NUCS presents a unique opportunity for the agriculture industry to capitalize on to combat food insecurity among indigenous or rural communities. NUCS's role in resolving the food insufficiency crisis has been validated in several research studies, including Nyadanu *et al.* (2014) and Magbagbeola *et al.* (2010). In terms of resources being scarce and providing competitive advantages, NUCS have some unique agronomic qualities that allow them to survive in a variety of ecological niches and adverse conditions such as poor soils and drought (Chivenge *et al.*, 2015). NUCS can also be used as a backup crop if the main crop fails or is unavailable, according to Mabhaudhi *et al.* (2011). NUCS are likewise one-of-a-kind and non-replaceable. Although NUCS can be found in both tropical and temperate climates, their function and significance are not widely recognized in many nations (; FAO, 2010; Padulosi *et al.*, 2013). As a result of the preceding debates, it is clear that Ethiopia's agricultural sector has not completely exploited NUCS as a plant resource, and that it requires immediate attention.

There is now a scarcity of information on the growth, development, nutritional value, and economic impact of neglected and indigenous crops. When such material does exist, it is frequently hidden away in indigenous knowledge systems and other ancient literature that is difficult to access. Furthermore, there has been little coordination on NUCS-related investigations, both on a regional and international basis. Because of the lack of

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coordination and uniformity of an umbrella word, there is little information available in search of environmental, food, and nutritional security, as well as the economic impact on NUCS (Amsalu et. al., 2008).

Fig 2: Challenges in underutilized crop production and promotion in Guto Gida district (Source: Computed from authors' field survey, 2021)

5.4.1.1. Policy Gaps

According to the results of this poll, existing policies do not expressly recognize NUS as a feasible option for attaining policy goals. To integrate NUS into mainstream agriculture, the existing institutional and policy environment must acknowledge the prospects for rural economic development that NUS provides. The results of a targeted research survey on identified and priority NUS, as well as demonstrated successes, will be used to develop a policy framework that (i) encourages a stable and underutilized crop and regulatory environment for NUS, and Kassie *et al.* (2018) encourages a stable and underutilized crop and regulatory environment for NUS. Kassie *et al.* (2018) support NUS capacity development, (iii) offer appropriate financial and material support for NUS RDI, and Mabhaudhi *et al.* (2019) encourage NUS to innovate in agro-processing technology. (John et al.) administration of resources, knowledge, and culture (v) increasing stakeholder involvement Mabhaudhi *et al.* (2019) managing the market and value chain Increased access to empirical data on NUS could be used to push for existing policies to be updated and/or strengthened so that they are explicit about the importance of Ethiopian agro-biodiversity—NUS. For example, the strategic grain reserves system, which now prioritizes maize and wheat, may be changed to include a larger range of underutilized crops and the cereals and legume crops already mentioned. Through the formal acknowledgment of a broader selection of crops, such inclusion

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would likewise address dietary diversity. Another example is ensuring that cross-cutting issues like the water-energy-food nexus, poverty, unemployment-inequality nexus, water-food-nutrition-health nexus, and agriculture-environment-health nexus are mainstreamed into new policies now being developed. NUS could become more widely recognized for the various functions that they can perform as a result of this mainstreaming.

5.4. 2. Opportunities for Promoting Underutilized Crops in Ethiopia

Various prospects for the promotion and growth of underused crop production have been reported or observed in the Guto Gida district, as well as in Ethiopia. The survey found that there is favorable production land and human power, that there is good/dense nutritional value, that there is high demand and high market value, that there is high social and cultural value, that it is safe for the environment, that it is tolerant to drought and stress conditions, that it is high productivity, that it is produced with local materials on a small area of land, and that it creates job opportunities for all members of the household (Fig 3). NUS have been demonstrated to have an essential role in the promotion of local livelihood, nutrition, and food security among indigenous groups in several studies conducted in remote parts of emerging countries (Baa-Poku, 2019). NUS has been recorded as a source of food and medicine throughout Asia and the Pacific countries, like India, Nepal, Malaysia, and the Philippines. NUS is also widely used in Sub-Saharan African countries like Malawi, Nigeria, Cote d'Ivoire, Uganda, and Zimbabwe (Padulosi *et al.*, 2013; FAO, 2010). Interest in NUS stems from a variety of concerns and needs, including their contribution to agricultural diversification, better use of marginal land and changing environments, food security and a more balanced diet, better safeguarding of our agro-biodiversity and associated cultural heritage, agricultural system self-sufficiency, an additional source of income for farmers, and job opportunities (Padulosi, 1998a).

There are calls for a paradigm shift in agriculture, with non-traditional pathways such as underutilized crops (NUS) being explored as potential future crops (Massawe *et al.*, 2015). This is based on findings that NUS is adaptable to a variety of agroecologies, is nutrient-dense, and offers greater chances in low-yielding locations (Mayes *et al.*, 2012; Chivenge *et al.*, 2015). As a result, their promotion in marginal agricultural production areas may increase rural people's availability and access to nutritious food (Gahukar, 2015). Their promotion in rural regions could also lead to the development of new value chains, which could lead to rural economic development (Mabhaudhi *et al.*, 2016a, 2017).

Importantly, NUS, which contains crop wild cousins, is a valuable source of germplasm for future crop advances such as nutritional value and abiotic and biotic stress tolerance (Castaeda-Alvarez *et al.*, 2016). Underutilized crops are an important part of local culture, are used in traditional food preparations, and are the focus of current culinary revival trends; they have advantages over staple crops in that they have been adapted to stressful environments and can be grown with low input and biological techniques (Mayes *et al.*, 2011).

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Fig 3: Opportunities for underutilized crop production and promotion (Source: Computed from authors' field survey, 2021)

A closer look at some of Ethiopia's food and agricultural policies and policy frameworks suggests that there is some potential to boost the production and use of underutilized crops in the country's development. Ethiopian Food and Nutrition Policy is one such policy framework (EFNP). The EFNP's main goals include: ensuring the availability, accessibility, and affordability of food in sufficient quantities and quality to meet the dietary needs of individuals in a sustainable manner; promoting good nutrition for the entire population; and ensuring the availability, accessibility, and affordability of food in sufficient quantities and quality to meet the dietary needs of individuals sustainably and ensuring food and income security at all levels for improving the nutrition as well as the socio-economic status of the population (Burchi *et al.*, 2011). The ENFP framework intends to stimulate and diversify the production of food commodities to meet the nutritional needs of households as one of the key ways of attaining its objectives (Capone *et al.*, 2014). It might be argued that diversifying food commodities to meet the dietary and nutritional needs of households, particularly those in rural and marginal areas, necessitates promoting underutilized crop production and consumption. The ENFP also expressly mentions the necessity to plan and conduct sensitization programs to popularize the production and use of under-exploited food crops to broaden the food base as a major approach for promoting and diversifying food commodity production (Garnett, 2013). This is a crucial policy statement that can be used to persuade the government to support the production and use of underused crops for national development.

The National Biotechnology and Biosafety Policy is another key policy framework that allows for the conservation, development, and utilization of underused crops (NBBP). Through the safe application of biotechnology, this policy framework aims to contribute to the national development goals of poverty eradication, improved healthcare, food security, industrialization, and environmental protection (Mtui and Reviews, 2011). The enhancement of biodiversity conservation and utilization is one of the key priority areas for this policy framework. The use of biotechnology to characterize indigenous plants to assess their economic potential for biotechnology applications is one of the ways to reach this goal (Penner, 2011). Because one of the major reasons for the underutilization and non-competitiveness of underutilized crops is a lack of or insufficient

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scientific information about their potential value, using biotechnology to characterize these crops and assess their economic potential is a critical opportunity for promoting their production and use in national development.

(NEMP) (Amsalu *et al.*, 2014) also offer significant prospects for encouraging underutilized crops in the country's growth. The NEMP strives to secure the conservation and sustainable management of Ethiopia's biological diversity, among other things. It proposes a variety of actions in this regard, including the enactment/reactivation of legislation to ensure the conservation of Ethiopian biodiversity in its broadest sense (Kassa, 2017). Biodiversity should be considered at the species, genetic, and ecosystem levels, according to one of the policy guiding principles. Although the NEMP does not directly include underutilized crops, it is clear that the generalized nature of its declarations and methods includes underutilized crops and their various species. From this perspective, the NEMP presents significant prospects for the conservation of Ethiopia's underutilized crop genetic diversity.

The National Agricultural Research Policy is another important agricultural-related policy framework that offers some options for promoting neglected crops. "To empower farmers by including them in defining and prioritizing their research needs and acquiring agricultural research services while technically and professionally advising them to make informed choices," says one of the policy framework's main goals. All farmers, particularly the poorest rural farmers, will be able to explain their research needs, including those linked to the cultivation of underutilized crops if they are adequately empowered.

6. Towards the Promotion of Ethiopia's Underutilized Crops

In addition to taking advantage of the opportunities given by the various policy instruments, as summarized in section 5 above, the following policy initiatives are recommended to promote and support the protection, production, and wider use of Ethiopia's underutilized crops.

6.1. Invest in Underutilized Crops Scientific Research and Innovation

One of the most important concerns in promoting underutilized crops is the need to enhance investment in scientific research and innovation. Scientific study and innovation are critical in determining their potential value, increasing their production capacity, and preserving their genetic resources. Underutilized crops deserve considerable attention in terms of scientific study and innovation, given their relevance in national development. It is advised that the government establish and sufficiently support a dedicated program focusing on scientific research and innovation for Ethiopia's underutilized crops to ensure that underutilized crops receive the essential research attention.

6.2. Ensure that the Public Extension System is maintained and improved

It was suggested that Ethiopia's policy, which advocates for a market-driven, private-sector-led agricultural extension and advisory services system, cannot meet the needs of poor farmers in marginal and fragile areas, where the majority of underutilized crops are farmed. Because underused crops play such an essential role in national development, the government should sustain and improve the public agricultural extension system to meet the requirements of the rural poor who have fostered and continue to raise them.

6.3. Strengthen the seed system for underutilized crops

Seed is the most significant and first input in any crop production chain and any agricultural production system in general. Ethiopia's government should address the seed needs of farmers farming underused crops as part of its ongoing seed policy formulation process. Protection and promotion of farmers' rights to guarantee the

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farmers' right to save and exchange seed, among other things; strengthening farmers' capacities in seed multiplication to improve the quality of seeds produced; and facilitating the development of local seed distribution networks are some of the measures that the government can take in this regard. The policy and strategy should also encourage public-private partnerships in the provision of enhanced seed to agricultural production areas that are marginal or isolated.

6.4. Invest in the Preservation and Protection of Traditional Knowledge and Culture

Many of Ethiopia's agricultural and food security strategies are unresponsive to underutilized crops. Many of them stimulate the displacement and replacement of underutilized crops with more competitive and marketable ones. As a result of this process, and as farmers with vital information about these crops continue to die, traditional knowledge and culture about underutilized crops are in grave danger of eroding and disappearing. Not only for the rural farmers who raise these crops but also for general scientific studies on crop development, traditional knowledge, and common culture linked with underutilized crops are extremely essential. Government investment in documentation is one of the most important ways to preserve and protect traditional knowledge linked with underused crops from extinction. In this context, the government should provide appropriate funding to the Plant Genetic Resources Centre so that it can properly carry out its crucial mission.

6.5. Incorporate underutilized crops into the agricultural production, processing, and marketing strategies.

The Zonal Agricultural Production, Agro-processing, and Marketing Strategy should be updated to intentionally bring underutilized crops on board as a crucial measure to encourage the production and wider use of underutilized crops. The underused crops that are to be included do not have to meet all of the criteria that were used to select the firms. It should be sufficient to say that they are regarded as extremely important by the local populations in terms of ensuring their food and nutrition security as well as providing them with cash. It is recommended that in each of the zones of production excellence, at least model underutilized crops of major food and income security importance should be brought on board to support their production, agro-processing, and marketing.

6.6. Underutilized crops should be included in the national export strategy.

The National Export Strategy should be updated to intentionally include some of Ethiopia's underutilized crops to promote the greater utilization of underutilized crops for increased earnings for the rural poor. Initially, the strategy should focus on increasing demand for these crops/species and their products in neighboring nations with comparable consumer tastes. In neighboring countries like Southern Sudan and Kenya, there is already a growing demand for Ethiopia's food products. As a result, Ethiopia should take advantage of this chance to export some of its underutilized commodities.

6.7. Adopt and put the Draft National Policy on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture into effect.

Many solid measures are included in the National Policy on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture, which, if adopted and effectively implemented, can help to promote the protection, development, and use of underutilized crops. Surveying and inventorying Ethiopia's, especially those for underutilized crops; developing community gene banks; developing orthodox seed conservation facilities; and developing the ability to assemble neglected, threatened, and underutilized species are just a few of these methods. The strategies also include the creation of a sui generis to protect traditional knowledge relevant to PGRFA, as well as the support and promotion of public awareness about the value of traditional crops and traditional and indigenous knowledge systems related to the conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA, the adoption of incentive

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measures to promote crop diversification, and the development of a sui generis to protect traditional knowledge relevant to PGRFA. In this context, the government is being urged to expedite the adoption of the national policy on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture.

7. Conclusion

For a long time, government policy has primarily focused on increasing the production and consumption of major crops. With Ethiopia's present agricultural and food security strategies and policy frameworks, this is still the case, according to this paper. Despite government support and investment in main crops, many Ethiopians, particularly the rural poor, have been unable to secure food and livelihoods. It is now time for government policy to pay attention to the underutilized crops of the poor. Underutilized crops have the ability to improve not just food and nutrition security but also income-generating opportunities, all of which are crucial for improving the livelihood security of Ethiopia's rural poor if given the required policy assistance. The government can take some policy actions to encourage the conservation, production, and greater use of underused crops, as outlined in this study.

The government must go beyond the economic considerations of underutilized crops when supporting them. The importance of these crops in ensuring food and nutrition security for Ethiopia's rural poor, who make up the majority of the country's population; their role in preserving and increasing biodiversity, which is essential for sustainable environmental management and agricultural production; and their adaptability to marginal environments and ability to stabilize fragile environments are all important considerations. In any event, many of Ethiopia's underutilized crops have significant commercial potential both nationally and internationally if given the necessary policy assistance in the fields of agricultural research, extension, agro-processing, and marketing. Now is the moment to invest in our rural poor's crops to ensure their food and livelihood security.

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Declarations

Author Contribution Statement

Dhaba Mengesha Adula: conceived and designed the experiments; performed the survey; analyzed and interpreted the data; wrote the paper.

Bogale Ayana analyzed and interpreted the data; wrote the paper.

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Data Availability Statement

Data will be made available on request.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest

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